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NEUROMARKETING IN THE SYSTEM OF MODERN COMMODITY SCIENCE: THE INFLUENCE OF PACKAGING DESIGN ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR

НЕЙРОМАРКЕТИНГ В СИСТЕМІ СУЧАСНОГО ТОВАРОЗНАВСТВА: ВПЛИВ ДИЗАЙНУ УПАКОВКИ НА ПОВЕДІНКУ СПОЖИВАЧА

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The article analyzes consumer behavior in terms of existing diversity and availability of goods. The authors noted the importance of the interaction of marketer and designer in creating packaging. The main factors influencing potential buyers, the motives that guide them when making purchasing decisions are identified. The role of packaging in the promotion and sale of products is analyzed, its functions are revealed. The basic requirements, criteria of design of packing are allocated. The authors substantiate the importance of investing resources in the process of its creation. The influence of the color scheme of the package on the physiological and mental state of a person is characterized. It is important to take into account the emotional impact of colors on consumer decisions about buying goods. The place of neuromarketing in modern commodity science is determined, its significance is revealed and the main characteristics are formulated. The essence of visual merchandising is considered. The directions of further research on this topic are indicated.

Keywords: neuromarketing, commodity science, consumer behavior, packaging, visual merchandising

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The huge number of similar products on store shelves suggests that it is unlikely that consumer purchase decisions are made on the basis of the original recipe, innovative processing system and other similar characteristics. They are certainly important, but first the consumer sees the packaging that he either likes, and the product intrigues him or does not like, and he passes by at best with a neutral attitude. Therefore, the development of packaging is very important, and this process should not be seen as a cost, but as one of the most profitable investments. Most companies in the market can compete effectively and successfully not only by using new products, production and consumption processes, but also by developing packaging with its innovative design [1].

According to some researches, in a typical supermarket, a customer inspects about 300 products per minute or one product every two tenths of a second. Thus, the only way to attract consumers to the product, in addition to merchandising techniques, is effective packaging. Product packaging is an integral part of the purchase. In most cases, attractive packaging can provoke impulsive purchases. The results of researches have shown that 76% of decisions to purchase goods are made "on the shelf", and 95% of them are made subconsciously [2]

Analysis of recent research and publications

The study of consumer behavior and the impact of packaging on it have paid attention to a large number of scientists over the years. Thorough works on this topic were written by A. Trindl, K. Moser, M. Lindstrom, P. Glimcher, etc. These issues were also considered by such scientists as O. Bilovodskaya, L. Sagach, G. Orlov, D. Levitska and others. However, the constant development of trade, the emergence of

new trends in the formation of consumer tastes and the deepening of research on the concept of "neuromarketing" indicate the relevance of this theme.

The aim of the article is to determine the place of neuromarketing in modern commodity science, the study of packaging as one of the most important factors of consumer choice, outlining important aspects in its creation.

The main part

When creating goods, manufacturers are primarily focused on maximizing customer satisfaction, trying to create its attractiveness. Products that are similar in design may differ significantly due to differences in the level of composition or materials, packaging design, additional services, distribution system and the nature of the advertising appeal. All these means of differentiation are used to influence consumer choice.

For consumer goods, the important carrier of information that can significantly influence consumer choice is the packaging of goods. That is why a lot of attention is paid to its creation, design and functionality. Confirmation and strengthening of product positioning becomes an important marketing task of packaging. Sometimes the cost of packaging is a very significant part of the cost of the product, as significant budgets are allocated for its creation and specialized agencies are involved.

The task of packaging is much broader than the function of storing goods. Packaging affects the perception of the quantity of goods inside, the freshness of the product, its environmental friendliness and usefulness. As we can see, it shapes consumers'

expectations of product consumption. Therefore, packaging is a carrier of information about the quality and basic consumer properties of the product.

Creating packaging requires the interaction of a marketer and a designer. Competently selected elements of packaging design (fonts, graphics, color solutions) are powerful psychological stimuli that affect the formation of consumer opinion and purchase. Depending on individual psychological, demographic and cultural characteristics, the elements of packaging design are perceived differently by consumers. Compliance of packaging design with a marketing strategy aimed at a particular target group of consumers is the basis for developing the concept of packaging. It also takes into account: the size and shape of the package, the number of packaging options for one product, packaging material, location, content and size of the label and the cost of packaging [3]

The packaging of the product, namely the appearance can not only attract but also repel. Between two almost identical products, the one with the most pronounced design of the package or label will always be chosen, the one that corresponds to the aesthetic preferences of the consumer. To understand the importance of packaging and its design, it is necessary to outline their main functions. Initially, packaging played its main functional role - to ensure the preservation of the original properties of products and goods during their life cycle, as well as to protect against adverse environmental conditions.

With the development of industry and the market, packaging began to perform more functions (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Packaging functions

Source: compiled by authors on materials [4].

The ability to transport and store products is still the main function of packaging, but we cannot ignore the functions of packaging that performs the design:

- to attract attention;
- leave a mark in memory;

— motivate the buyer to choose the product offered to him [4].

The growing role of packaging as a marketing tool is due to the influence of various factors (Table 1).

Basic requirements for the design of modern packaging are (Fig. 2).

Table 1. Factors influencing the role of packaging as a marketing tool

Factor	The essence of the factor
Self-service	Effective packaging attracts attention, emphasizes the features of the product, inspires consumer confidence and creates a general pleasant impression of it
Consumer welfare	Improving consumer welfare means that buyers are willing to pay extra for the convenience, attractiveness, reliability and prestige of improved packaging
Company image and trademark	Attention is drawn to the packaging, which provides instant recognition of the company or brand

Source: compiled by authors on materials [11].

Often the product becomes popular due to packaging. A well-thought-out design can help the user to use the product or use the product in the most convenient way. Thus, individual packaging in some cases is provided with dispensers, brushes, sponges, etc. The packaging ensures the safe use of the product, for example, with

elements that restrict access to young children. Winning packaging design allows you to differentiate the product of the shelf on its appearance, which is especially important today, when coming to the shops, we are lost from the large amount of information and variety on the shelves.

Figure 2. Basic requirements for modern packaging design

Source: compiled by authors on materials [4].

Designers use color, pattern and shape to capture the distracted attention of the buyer and use packaging to attract him to the product. Their task is not so much to guarantee quality as to ensure multiple purchases. Packaging should not just leave the shelf, but also attract the attention of people who are interested in it and will buy it again and again. Hence the conclusion – the design of packaging is the basis for the promotion of the product, in fact, is one of the leading criteria by which the consumer chooses in favor of a product. Competent design of packaging products is the most powerful tool of visual communication. It is one of the main motives for making the right purchase. [4]

Most modern consumers want to buy innovative packaging. This is due to the constant modernization and updating of the product range. Especially interesting for the market are innovative product packaging that combines high mechanical and barrier

properties, external attractiveness, manufacturability and environmental friendliness. If the packaging design is developed in the context of positioning the product, brand and advertising campaign, it gives good results, especially financial. Packaging should represent the brand as expressively as possible, so that buyers at a glance understand what products they see in front of them. Design decisions cannot be isolated from the very philosophy of the brand and product positioning. The law of "design in context" has the opposite effect – if the packaging will not represent the characteristics of the brand or product, the consumer will believe at most once. The client wants respect from the company. And if the buyer does not find such a beautiful product as it is drawn and written on the package, he does not perceive it positively enough.

Consider the main criteria in the design of packaging (table 2).

Table 2. Main criteria in packaging design

Criterion	Essence
1	2
Originality and simplicity in packaging design	According to many studies, the packaging on the supermarket shelf has 3 seconds to attract the attention of the consumer. During this time, the consumer will see the form, draw an analogy with advertising, look at pictures and possibly read the capital letters. After that, there will be or did not want to get acquainted with the product closer. Most modern companies create both original

Continuation of Table 2.

1	2
	and simple packaging. Some experts point out that the most important thing when designing packaging is to be unpredictable, because there are many stereotypical solutions on the market. The basis may be the innovation of the product itself or novelty in brand positioning. The main thing is to move away from templates.
"Healthy" design	People take care of their health. Consumers are increasingly educated in medicine, in the troubles of their body, take into account the usefulness of products. This trend is leading to some changes in graphic design. First, the packaging is perceived positively if it is made of safe materials and taking into account the peculiarities of storage of goods. For the consumer, the information on the packaging about the product itself, its composition, hygiene standards, recommendations of various institutes and ministries, the deadline for implementation is becoming increasingly important. Also, so-called organic products are becoming increasingly important. Of course, they also require special packaging. If we mention "design in context", it is the packaging that should convey the idea of a healthy natural product. Experts point out that when designing, it is useful to use elements and colors that are associated with health and naturalness. It is also important to improve not only the emotional component of the package, but also its storage capacity. Because consumers value healthy foods, packaging that can retain the product's beneficial properties better and longer is a success.
Convenient design	Many trends in packaging design are related not only to competition in the market, but also to changing consumers. In recent years, society is increasingly focused on convenience. This is due to the value and lack of time, increasing the number of office workers, etc. The trend is especially important for food, because people are less and less preparing food for someone other than themselves. And they themselves value their time and convenient goods. It can be noted that the main aspects of ease of use of packaging are: ease of use (availability), ease of storage, ease of use for special purposes, ease of disposal, reusability, impact on the environment. Packaging can make goods more adapted to the intensive life of the customer. For example, you can mention yogurts and juices in plastic bottles or cartons. This is convenient, because now you can buy such a product, drink a little and put in a bag and not be afraid that the liquid may spill. It is also important to analyze the convenience of the product at different stages of consumption - when transported home, stored or used directly. Therefore, when designing a package, you should think carefully about how convenient it is for the consumer to use the product in different situations, store it and transport it home.
Packaging as part of the product	Nowadays, you can hear the phrase "smart packaging" - this is also an example of how the packaging itself can complement the product. People still have a habit of using home packaging - in many families, packaging is used after use. For example, metal boxes are used to store flour or cereals, glass jars - for canning. Therefore, it is also an opportunity to differentiate your packaging from competitors.

Source: compiled by authors on materials [1].

The process of creating effective packaging is especially important for new products, because the goal in such cases is to convey to the target audience an advertising message that can influence consumer choice, for example, through the use of rational motives (health, reliability, low price, etc.) or emotional motives. (nostalgia, patriotism, assimilation to "stars", etc.). Therefore, consumer choice can be influenced by the external attractiveness of advertising packaging, which visualizes the differences between the product and competitors due to the shape of packaging (bottles, labels, etc.) or its design solution (color combinations, bright images of characters on the package, etc.).

Even small differences in advertising packaging can play a crucial role in consumer choice between competing products. Modern advertising packaging should be convenient not only for consumers but also for manufacturers and sellers, as unusual packaging

can be inconvenient from a logistical point of view (for example, a box of goods takes up more space than it could take in a traditional packaging solution), or create inconveniences for retail, take up too much space on supermarket shelves, etc. However, such inconveniences will take a back seat if the new packaging design provides effective communication with consumers and the product in the new packaging sells better [5].

Packaging not only promotes the introduction of new products into everyday life, but also introduces into our consciousness certain stereotypes of consumption, forms household priorities, and even, to some extent, programs the way of life. Therefore, it is not surprising that his role in society is growing every year [6].

Modern advertising is becoming more and more an art, and to make it high quality and effective, you need to know the target audience of the product as well as

possible. Advertising prepares the buyer to meet with the product, and packaging plays the biggest role at the time of purchase. The design techniques used in advertising can evoke both positive and negative feelings in the consumer, convey to him at the level of perception of information that will correlate with the main content of the advertising message or completely deny it. [7]

Human consciousness and subconsciousness primarily feels the color and shape of the visible object, these are the basic elements of human perception. In Europe and the United States, there is a whole branch of marketing that deals with the selection of colors for goods. Everything is important: aesthetic component, traditions, stereotypes, psychology of color perception, etc. Thanks to the rules of composition, nuances of color, adequate selection of forms, the artist-designer implements the content that is embedded in the marketing tool (for example, in packaging or advertising). Errors in the selection of colors can significantly reduce sales of goods, as the physical properties of colors, the laws of their relationship with nature and the modern environment have a physiological and mental impact on humans [8].

Today there are three types of color effects on humans:

- physical (physiological);
- optical;
- emotional.

The colors are divided into:

- chromatic (colors and their shades, which a person distinguishes in the spectrum - red, orange, yellow, green, blue, dark blue, purple, which are determined by three parameters: color tone, saturation and brightness);
- achromatic (white, shades of gray, black, which are characterized only by the amount of reflected light).

Color tone and saturation are qualitative parameters of color, and brightness is quantitative. Determining the color based on these parameters is useful because it combines the qualities of colors that are easy to distinguish with the human eye. A person's perception of color is subjective and depends, for example, on the environment, mood or mixing of several colors.

When choosing a color scheme for the product or its packaging must be taken into account (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Aspects to take into account when creating packaging
Source: compiled by authors on materials [7].

The specifics of the target audience for which the product is intended should be taken into account so that, for example, for a "premium" product, the colors should be "solid", "expensive", which limits the use of an expanded palette of colors; daily consumer goods do not require any special elegant shapes, and there are more opportunities to experiment with color.

Ensuring the integrity of the product and its color support is expressed in the fact that the consumer perceives the design of the product or its packaging as a whole, rarely focusing on small details.

Individuality is that you should not imitate competitors, but it is desirable to find your own style.

When choosing a color for the design of the product, it is advisable to take into account which group of buyers it will be aimed at, taking into account the main characteristics of the psychological portrait of the consumer - for example, dividing buyers into impulsive, economical or traditional. So, red, orange or

bright blue make you want to buy the product immediately. The segment of "economical" buyers like blue and blue-green shades. For traditional buyers, you should use light blue and pink shades. That is why when planning and launching a new product you need to consult with a professional colorist. It should also be borne in mind that color not only helps to sell the product, but also ensures its prestige (natural color of mahogany, metallic luster of technical equipment, etc.). Of course, this theory must be adjusted to the nuances of a particular field of activity, the characteristics of the target audience and other factors.

However, we can safely say about the emotional impact of colors in two ranges – cool and warm. Warm colors are literally used to "warm up" the consumer audience. They have a stimulating effect on the psyche, cause a surge of energy, speed up breathing and heart rate. Unlike red, yellow, orange, which are the colors of impulsive shopping, the cool range of colors reduces

the activity of emotions, relaxes and calms. Cool shades make you forget about possible losses and costs, they set up for trusting communication, so the wise use of blue, green and dark blue colors can actively stimulate sales [8].

According to some researchers, consumers prefer packaging with colors that match the characteristics of the product. On the other hand, the use of colors unusual in the design of packaging, unusual for a particular product category, may be a deliberate advertising technique aimed at creating in the perception of consumers different products from competitors, because the packaging of competing products has some similarities, traditional design solutions, color choices etc. One of the effective ways to influence the target audience and stand out among competing products is a new visual packaging solution, which must take into account the peculiarities of the target audience's perception of color combinations and corporate characters (people, animals, fictional creatures, etc.) which may also be on the packaging or label [5].

It is also important how consumers read the text from a distance, whether they have the opportunity to see and pay attention to it. A study by the British Color Council found that it is best to read the inscription in yellow on black, black – on orange, yellow and vice versa [1]. The larger the font, the more likely it is that a person will notice the product. The shape of the font is also important, because a neat and unusual font is perceived by a person with greater aesthetic pleasure than usual [11].

Manufacturers also use a limited series of their products in appropriately designed packaging as a means of attracting the attention of the target audience. The advertising campaign of the limited series of the product attracts the attention of consumers to the brand as a whole and to the whole range of goods or services of the company. Packaging transmits an advertising message to the target audience, which is based on the use of rational or emotional motives. The colors that dominate the design of advertising packaging identify the brand and create an emotional connection with the target audience [5].

Each company strives for its individuality, which would ensure its successful communication with the consumer. Visual individuality allows you to stand out from the competition and increase consumer awareness of the company. Corporate identity is a powerful means of identification and plays a very important role in creating, first of all, the logo of the organization. But still it is important to choose a color scheme not only for the logo, but also for the corporate image as a whole.

Color makes corporate identity elements more attractive, evokes the right emotions in consumers for the company and helps them remember it better. A person's mood and his attitude to one or another color does not play any role in the psycho-physiological influence of colors on him. It does not matter - like or dislike the color, still the specifics and nature of its impact remains unchanged, regardless of the state of the organism at the time of exposure. Although it is

difficult to disagree with the opinion that the culture and traditions of the region in which they are used are also important in the perception of colors.

The principle of color selection is harmony based on contrasting or soft color ratios. Color harmony is the harmony of colors with each other as a result of the found proportionality of color areas, their balance and harmony, based on finding a unique shade of each color. The play of color can evoke a variety of sensations. For example, hot colors are aggressive and attract attention, so they are widely used in the field of packaging design and advertising. It has been proven that red is a stimulant, increases activity, determination and body temperature. Red is the basis of warm colors, but unlike hot ones, they are softened by the addition of yellow. These colors directly affect the sphere of emotions, balance, adjust to sociability and it seems that they touch the soul.

Cold colors calm the metabolic process in the body, so some people in a room kept in cool tones, may experience even a slight chill. The effect of deep blue is sometimes powerful and severe, but at the same time refreshing and pure. Unlike hot colors, blue does not cause negative emotions.

Dark colors (brown, navy blue, etc.) in graphic design are used as a contrast for lighter colors, because they are able to convey many shades of mood – from confidence and restraint to gloomy melancholy. Light colors can hardly be called colors in the full sense of the word, they are so light and transparent that they are perceived only as a slight hint of color. In the same way, pale colors are, rather, shades (located in the central ring of the color wheel). They seem gentle, soft, pastel, evoking associations with innocence, youth and romanticism. These colors are considered "feminine", they are used to create perfume packaging, cosmetics.

The basis of cool colors is blue, but in contrast to the cold they are added yellow and red, which gives a rich range of green, blue and purple shades. They are perceived as soothing, soothing and thought-provoking. Bright colors – expressive and clean, without a clear admixture of white and black. These colors give dynamism and energy in graphic and advertising design [9].

Today in the world of marketing there is a revolution called neuromarketing, which uses various stimuli that affect the human brain to cause the desired action. This science is based on human brain research and classical marketing data, which found that consumers make decisions not only based on rational judgments, but also on emotional reactions that they cannot control. This means that knowing the biochemistry of customer's emotional reactions, sellers can effectively influence all five human senses by applying positive stimuli such as smell, music, color, merchandising, which positively affect the mood and purchasing power of shoppers, as a result. improve sales strategy. This is why the concept of neuromarketing as a new method of defining and predicting consumer behavior has recently become more common in marketing theory and practice.

The overall flow of outdoor advertising is so great that consumer audiences experience visual and

auditory fatigue, advertising effectiveness is significantly reduced, and advertisers need to find unconventional approaches to studying consumer thought and behavior, one of which is neuromarketing. Neuromarketing is one of the most effective modern technologies, based on statistical processing of data obtained in the process of psychophysiological research. The object of the study of neuromarketing is a wide range of reactions in human behavior: the study of changes in pulse dynamics, sweating, brain currents, pupil movements and other spontaneous reactions, actively uses magnetic resonance imaging of the brain [10].

Visual merchandising is a type of neuromarketing that studies the effects of color and images. Many scientists have paid attention to the issue of visual perception of the product, for example, Arndt Trayndl in his book "Neuromarketing. Visualization of emotions", Klaus Moser "Psychology of marketing and advertising", Martin Lindstrom "Brand Sense" and others. Recently, most attention has been paid to issues of color, which are very relevant in the works of Alexander Lebedev-Lyubimov, Paul Glimcher, Lyubov Ryumshina and others. The general opinion of all these scientists is that the impact on consumer choice through visual perception is very relevant at the present stage of development of market relations. The main factors that contribute to the effective promotion and consumption of goods are: the ability to purchase, usefulness, price, quality, service life, shape, design, brand and of course – packaging [11].

Consumers are pleased to consider themselves rational people who are able to make various decisions on their own, despite the pressure of the environment. And although buyers may take into account other people's opinions, the final decision to buy the product, in their opinion, they make themselves. Although, in fact, decision-making is influenced by many different factors, including biology, psychology and the environment. Marketers and psychologists have studied cognitive bias for years, along with ways to spread different ideas, so neuromarketing is used as a

method of influencing consumer behavior, from design development, use of its techniques in advertising and ending with movies. An interesting example of the use of neuromarketing in design is research from Frito Lay, a company that makes Lay's chips. It showed that the use of natural and matte colors, as well as photos of healthy products do not motivate to buy, so the company began to use a shiny package of bright colors with the image of fried chips. Manipulation of the consumer's subconscious leads to increased sales and profits [10].

Neuromarketing studies consumer behaviour: thinking, cognition, memory, emotional reactions, etc., with the goal of predicting consumer choice. It allows you to determine the consumer's attitude to the product even before he realized it. This is one of the main differences between neuromarketing and traditional marketing: it does not require the collection and analysis of data on the subjective preferences of the buyer. In the study through traditional marketing – surveys and questionnaires – respondents are not always honest in their answers, while the methods of neuromarketing research look directly into the human brain [12].

Conclusion

The congestion of the modern world with the amount of advertising, and, as a consequence, insensitivity of people to it, encourages the search for new ways to attract attention to the product. The impact of packaging on the consumer is undeniable. The choice to buy depends on the shape of the package, color scheme, font on it and many other elements. Neuromarketing is a set of methods for studying consumer behaviour that allows you to predict and influence the decisions of a potential buyer without the need to collect data on his subjective preferences. That is why, in order to effectively promote a product on the market, it is necessary to conduct research in neuromarketing to study and expand the possibilities of its application.

Abstract

The article analyzes consumer behavior in terms of existing diversity and availability of goods. Many researchers have studied the behavior of consumers and the impact of packaging on it for many years. However, the constant development of trade, the emergence of new trends in the formation of consumer tastes and the deepening of research on the concept of "neuromarketing" indicate the relevance of this topic. The aim of the article is to determine the place of neuromarketing in modern commodity science, the study of packaging as one of the most important factors of consumer choice, outlining important aspects in its creation. For consumer goods, the important carrier of information that can significantly influence consumer choice is the packaging of goods. In most cases, attractive packaging can provoke impulsive purchases. That is why a lot of attention is paid to its creation, design and functionality. Competently selected elements of packaging design (fonts, graphics, color solutions) are powerful psychological stimuli that affect the formation of consumer opinion and purchase. The authors noted the importance of the interaction of marketer and designer in creating packaging. Compliance of packaging design with a marketing strategy aimed at a particular target group of consumers is the basis for developing the concept of packaging. The packaging of the product, namely the appearance, can not only attract but also repel the consumer. Between two almost identical products, the one with the most pronounced design of the package or label will always be chosen, the one that corresponds to the aesthetic preferences of the consumer. The authors identify the main factors influencing potential buyers, the motives that guide them when making purchasing decisions. The role of packaging in the promotion and sale of products is analyzed, its functions are revealed. The basic requirements, criteria of design of packing are allocated. The importance of investing resources

in the process of its creation is substantiated. The influence of the color scheme of the package on the physiological and mental state of a person is characterized. It is important to take into account the emotional impact of colors on consumer decisions about buying goods. The place of neuromarketing in modern commodity science is determined, its significance is revealed and the main characteristics are formulated. The essence of visual merchandising as a type of neuromarketing that studies aspects of the influence of color and images is considered. The directions of further research on this topic are indicated.

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